

**Support Uptake Integrated
Pest Management and Low-
Risk Pesticide Use**

Deliverable: D1.2
**Monitoring system for a holistic assessment of
the impact of current crop protection versus
IPM strategies (M30)**

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Executive summary of the deliverable

The SUPPORT project has developed the SUPPORT IPM Monitoring Tool (SIM), a web-based decision-support system designed to facilitate the holistic assessment of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies at the field and farm level across various European cropping systems. The primary objective of this deliverable was to create a multi-criteria assessment tool that enables stakeholders—including farmers, advisors, policymakers, and supply chain actors—to evaluate and compare crop protection strategies based on environmental, economic, agronomic, and social indicators, with a particular focus on pesticide-related risks.

The SIM tool is structured into three core modules—Site Definition, Application Scenarios, and Analysis—allowing users to define detailed management practices and compare real or hypothetical strategies over time and space. Key indicators assessed include greenhouse gas emissions, pesticide use frequency, active ingredients used, total costs, and pesticide load (PL-EU)—a comprehensive component capturing the environmental fate, ecotoxicology, and human health impacts of pesticides. The tool integrates data from ten project partner countries covering eight crops, with each country providing both state-of-the-art and IPM-based management scenarios derived from the strategy designs in Deliverable 4.2. The scenario comparison outputs generated by the tool for each crop/country combination were discussed with each NCC, marking this as the first validation round.

The actual deliverable: the SUPPORT IPM Monitoring Tool (SIM) is written and coded in Java and is freely available for registered users at <http://synops.julius-kuehn.de/support> (See Chapter 6 for the user guide).

Methodologically, the tool builds on established frameworks such as SYNOPS, MiLA, and the Danish Pesticide Load model, leveraging large-scale datasets (e.g., KTBL, PPDB, Ecoinvent) and expert-validated field practices to compute accurate and regionally relevant indicators. It supports quantitative scenario comparison and includes exportable outputs for further analysis.

The SIM tool contributes significantly to enhancing transparency, knowledge exchange, and decision-making in sustainable crop protection. It provides a practical and scientifically robust platform for monitoring IPM uptake and its impacts, supporting EU policy goals on pesticide reduction, biodiversity conservation, and food system resilience. Importantly, this deliverable includes a comprehensive User Guide, ensuring that users across stakeholder groups can navigate and utilize the tool effectively.

Looking ahead, the next phase in the development of the SIM Tool will focus on stakeholder validation and tool refinement. A second validation round is scheduled for July and August 2025, during which NCC partners will independently explore the tool and generate results to become familiar with its functionalities. Feedback gathered during this phase will inform the third Focus Group meeting, as part of the internal WP4 meeting, in September 2025, providing a platform for NCC partners to share their experiences and suggest improvements. Minor adjustments to the tool's interface and documentation will be implemented accordingly, in preparation for the third and final round of national Focus Groups taking place between October and December 2025. These sessions will engage stakeholders in co-developing future and novel IPM strategies adopting future IPM tools that currently are in their initial phases in terms of development and/or implementation by using the SIM Tool. The insights gained will be analysed and feed into an updated version of the tool, to be released in October 2026.

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
GA	The General Assembly
CA	Consortium Agreement
SC	Scientific Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Officer
PMT	The Project Management Team
EB	Executive Board (Core Team)
WP	The Work Package
WPL	The Work Package Leader
TL	Task leader
NCC	National Crop Cluster
CoP	Community of Practices
NoP	Network of Practices
PAB	Project Advisory Board
SCT	Scientific Coordination Team
DoA	Description of the action
IPM	Integrated Pest Management
AI	Active Ingredient
PPP	Plant Protection Product
PL	Pesticide Load
GHG	Greenhouse Gases

1. Introduction

Pesticides play an important role in managing food production by securing crop yields, through prevention and eradication of harmful organisms¹. Existing crop protection strategies rely largely on the use of chemical pesticides² which may carry hazardous substances that may pose risks for human health, biodiversity and for the environment. Exposure to some pesticides in an occupational context³, through respiration by bystanders or through residues found on food and in drinking water⁴, can lead to significant health issues⁴. Pesticide use can also adversely affect the environment, via air, water and soil pollution, leading to damaging effects on habitats and the quality of ecosystem services⁵. In addition, pesticides can impact non-target species, resulting in biodiversity loss at a local, population or genetic level, as well as causing indirect effects within the food chain⁶ and changes in ecosystem dynamics (e.g., absence of natural predators)⁷. Another area of concern relates to the emergence of pesticide resistance, which can have economic, environmental, and eventually public health consequences⁸. Therefore, to protect biodiversity, the environment and human health, there is a widely felt need to reduce the use of pesticides and to reduce the dependence of agricultural producers on the use of chemical pesticides without reducing food production and farm economic profitability and the provision of other ecosystem services. Future strategies and policies need to be developed to reduce the use and risks of pesticides, supporting agricultural production and food security and encouraging the development and adoption of sustainable practices.

Well-designed integrated pest management programmes (IPM) can play an important role to reduce the dependency on chemical pesticides. However, the uptake of IPM practices by farmers remains low, creating a challenge to support uptake of those techniques. We lack knowledge about the reasons why the gap between potential and realised uptake of IPM practices exists, and which pathways can bridge this gap. While trade-offs in pesticide use have been widely debated in society and policy⁷, a range of factors may shape agricultural production in the future and hence influence not only pesticide use and associated consumer concerns⁹ but also agricultural yield and farmer livelihoods¹⁰.

Against this backdrop, EU policy on pesticides use needs to remove or avoid barriers, to create opportunities and to integrate the aims of different stakeholder groups to achieve the overall vision of safeguarding human health and protecting the environment, whilst achieving the required levels of agricultural production and supporting trade. Policy makers have responded to such challenges by regulating the use of pesticides in the Sustainable Use Directive 2009/128/EC (SUD), which brought relevant innovations to the pesticide framework such as, but not limited to, the concept of IPM and its eight principles¹¹. However, evaluation studies have clearly identified challenges in the implementation of IPM policy¹².

A wide range of digital tools has been developed to support Integrated Pest Management (IPM), particularly internet-based decision support systems (DSS). However, their uptake among farmers remains limited due to technical constraints, lack of trust, and differing user perceptions¹³⁻¹⁴. Despite the availability of these tools, their integration into practical farm management remains low, limiting the transition toward more sustainable pesticide use. In parallel, sustainability assessment tools such as DEXiPM¹⁵⁻¹⁶ and SustainOS¹⁷ are used to evaluate the environmental, economic, and social performance of IPM strategies through decision-tree approaches and expert-based, semi-quantitative indicators. While valuable, these tools often lack detailed consideration of the environmental risks associated with pesticide use. Tools like the SYNOPSIS-WEB risk indicator¹⁸ address this gap but are currently limited to specific regions and local applications. To support the wider implementation of sustainable IPM across the EU, there is a need to advance and scale such tools.

In response to these challenges, the SUPPORT project has initiated the development of the web-based SUPPORT IPM Monitoring Tool (SIM) under Task 1.2, designed to enable integrated and scenario-based assessments of IPM strategies at the field and farm level. This tool draws on established high-level indicators to evaluate environmental, economic, agronomic, and social impacts, with a particular focus on pesticide-related risks such as environmental fate, ecotoxicity, and human health. The SIM tool allows transparent comparison of both real and hypothetical crop protection strategies across diverse cropping systems and regions. It is intended to support decision-making by a wide range of stakeholders—including farmers, advisors, supply chain actors, and policymakers—contributing to the wider implementation of sustainable IPM practices in Europe.

2. Objective

The main objective is to develop a monitoring system based on multi-criteria assessment for the holistic evaluation of IPM strategies. Designed to be transparent, user-friendly, and applicable across various crops, cropping systems, and regions, the system will support stakeholders including farmers, advisors, supply chain actors, and policymakers in assessing the impact of adopting IPM. The outcomes will contribute to (i) assessing current and future IPM scenarios developed in Task 4.2 making use of the IPM Inventory developed in Task 1.1 (Task 1.3); and (ii) will feed into the policy recommendations that SUPPORT will develop (Task 3.3).

3. Methods

The methodology of the SUPPORT IPM Monitoring Tool is based on the need for a comprehensive yet practical framework that integrates multiple dimensions of IPM assessment, as outlined in the project objectives. Conceptually, the tool is designed to facilitate a holistic evaluation of IPM strategies by combining environmental, economic, agronomic, and social indicators, thereby addressing the complexity of crop protection decision-making. This monitoring system builds on existing high-level indicators—such as SYNOPS¹⁸ and the Danish Pesticide Load¹⁹—to provide an integrated assessment of IPM strategies across environmental (environmental fate of pesticides, pesticide impact on the environment, greenhouse gas emissions), economic (total costs), agronomic (yield, frequency of pesticide applications and number of active ingredients applied), and social dimensions (pesticide impact on human health). The scope of the tool includes detailed documentation of all relevant field operations, allowing users to compare both actual management practices and hypothetical scenarios at the field or farm level, over single or multiple years. While the tool focuses extensively on pesticide-related risks by assessing environmental fate, ecotoxicological impacts, and human health considerations, it excludes factors such as fertilizer use due to their limited variability within typical crop protection strategies.

3.1 The web-based tool SUPPORT IPM Monitoring Tool

SUPPORT IPM Monitoring Tool (SIM) is written and coded in Java and is freely available for registered users at <http://synops.julius-kuehn.de/support>. In chapter 6 of this document a user guide is presented. SIM consists of three separate modules:

3.1.1 Site definition

Users can select agricultural fields directly from an interactive map interface. The integration of mapping services such as Google Earth and OpenStreetMap enables intuitive and accurate localization of the relevant field area.

3.1.2 Application scenarios

This module enables users to define detailed management scenarios for specific crops. It allows the entry of a comprehensive set of agricultural operations performed throughout the cropping cycle, such as sowing, tillage, fertilization, pesticide application, harvesting, and other mechanical interventions including mulching, flaming, or harrowing. These operations are systematically organized into six categories: Sowing, Pesticide Application, Non chemical control measures, Tillage, Harvest, and Catch/Cover crops.

Each operation can be further specified by selecting the machinery used. The system supports the inclusion of detailed agronomic and economic data, such as seeding density (seeds/m²), cost of fuel (€/litre), labour wages (€/hour), and estimated crop yield (t/ha). By capturing both technical and economic inputs, this module allows users to construct realistic and context-specific management scenarios. For pesticide applications, the user enters each with information on the application date and the properties of the spray equipment (drift reduction %), percentage of area sprayed and buffer zones. Subsequently, information about the applied pesticides are added for each application either as active ingredients or as commercial products. The user manually enters the application rate of the PPP or AI.

3.1.3 Analysis Module

The analysis module processes the input scenarios to compute a set of indicators, as defined in Table 1. Each scenario is defined by a unique combination of crop, field, and management practices.

The module supports comparative analysis, allowing users to evaluate multiple scenarios for the same crop and field. Results can be presented in both tabular and graphical formats, facilitating a clear assessment across scenarios. Furthermore, users can export the complete set of calculated indicators as a CSV file for further external analysis.

Table 1: Complete list of indicators assessed in the SIM Tool with descriptions

Indicator	Description
Total GHG emissions per hectare	Represents the total greenhouse gas emissions (expressed in CO ₂ equivalents) associated with machinery operations per hectare. This includes emissions resulting from fuel consumption and equipment use throughout the cropping cycle, including all field operations such as sowing, pesticide application (also the emissions associated with the production of pesticides) and harvest, among others. Only machinery-related GHG emissions are included; emissions from soil processes or production of fertilizers are not accounted for in this tool
Total costs	Reflects the overall economic cost per scenario, encompassing both operational costs (e.g., diesel consumption, machinery working time, and labor wages) and input costs (e.g., pesticides and other agricultural products). It considers all field operations such as sowing, pesticide application and harvest, among others.

Frequency of PPP application	Indicates the number of pesticide application events carried out over the course of the cropping cycle and for each of the four groups of pesticides. It accounts for each instance a machine enters the field to apply plant protection products.
Number of Pesticide Products	The total number of different pesticide products used during a cropping cycle and for each of the four groups of pesticides. A product used multiple times is still counted only once.
Number of Active Ingredients	The total number of different active ingredients contained in all pesticide products used during the cropping cycle and for each of the four groups of pesticides.
PLEU Fate	Assesses the environmental fate of applied pesticides, including factors such as degradation, leaching, runoff, and persistence in soil and water systems.
PLEU Ecotoxicology	Estimates the potential toxic effects of pesticides on non-target organisms in the environment, including aquatic life, beneficial insects, and soil organisms.
PLEU Human Health	Evaluates the potential risks pesticides may pose to human health, including exposure risks for operators and consumers.

3.2 Data

Project partners from ten different countries provided data for field operations for a total of eight different crops (Table 2). Each country contributed data for two to three crops, depending on regional relevance. These operations represent a full crop cycle and include all typical field measures carried out in that region. The data was based on putative strategies described in Deliverable 4.2 and was validated by farm advisors to ensure accuracy. Each scenario includes the timing and description of all field interventions, along with machinery specifications such as working width, spray tank capacity, and engine power. It also detailed all pesticide applications, including the product or active ingredient used, application dose, and the percentage of the surface area treated. For each crop–country combination, at least two scenarios were developed:

State of the Art – representing the current conventional practices.

IPM – incorporating selected IPM measures.

In many cases, a third or more scenarios were included, representing a variant of the IPM strategy— for example, with or without tillage, or incorporating other specific agronomic modifications.

Table 2: Overview of data collected during the first validation round from ten countries and eight crops, used as input for the tool

Country	Crop	Strategies for each scenario	Scenarios	Total Number of scenarios
Germany	Potato	3 (Early Potatoes/ Storage/ Starch)	2 (State of Art / IPM Improved)	6
	Wheat	1	3 (State of Art/ IPM improved no tillage / IPM improved with tillage)	3
Italy	Apple	2 (High density open field/ Low density open field)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4
	Olive	2 (High density open field/ Low density open field)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4

	Onion	2 (Short day/ Long day)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4
Poland	Apple	2 (High density open field/ Low density open field)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4
	Onion	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
	Potato	3 (Seed/ Consumption/ Storage)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	6
Romania	Maize	2 (Conventional/ Organic)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4
	Wheat	2 (Conventional/ Organic)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4
Switzerland	Maize	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
	Wheat	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
Greece	Olive	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
	Wine Grape	No data received		
Belgium	Potato	3 (Seed/ Consumption/ Storage)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	6
	Strawberry	No data received		
Denmark	Maize	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
	Potato	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
	Wheat	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
Netherlands	Apple	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
	Potato	3 (Seed/ Consumption/ Starch)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	6
	Strawberry	2 (Indoor Production/ Mixed Nursery System)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4
Spain	Olive	2 (Rain fed/ Irrigated)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4
	Strawberry	1	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	2
	Wine Grape	2 (Dryland/Irrigated)	2 (State of Art/ IPM Improved)	4

3.3 GHG Emissions

This tool calculates greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from field operations using the Model for Integrated Life Cycle Assessment in Agriculture (MiLA), developed by ZALF²⁰. It allows users to document all key field operations involved in crop cultivation, including tillage, sowing, mechanical weeding, pesticide application and harvesting.

To estimate diesel use for each operation, the tool relies on the Field Work Calculator online database, developed by KTBL²¹. This database provides diesel consumption values based on the type of machinery used (including working width and engine performance), as well as the quantities of seed, pesticide, and crop yield involved.

3.3.1. GHG Emissions from Diesel Combustion

The tool calculates CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O emissions from diesel combustion based on the IPCC Tier 1 methodology²².

3.3.2. GHG Emissions from Diesel and Machinery Production

It also includes GHG emissions associated with the production of diesel and agricultural machinery. These values are sourced from the Ecoinvent database v3.1²³.

3.3.3. Seed Production

The tool accounts for GHG emissions generated during seed production. Emission factors are also taken from Ecoinvent v3.1²³.

3.3.4 Pesticide Production

Similarly, GHG emissions from the production of pesticides are included. MiLA integrates a list of 770 commonly used pesticides in Europe, with emissions calculated by aggregating the GHG outputs of individual pesticide ingredients based on Ecoinvent v3.1 data²³.

Note: This tool exclusively includes machinery-related GHG emissions. Emissions from soil processes are not considered.

3.4 Costs

The economic evaluations in the SUPPORT tool are based on the Field Work Calculator online database, developed by KTBL²¹. This calculator estimates the costs of agricultural field operations by integrating technical specifications with economic parameters, providing cost indicators per hectare or per hour for a wide range of activities such as ploughing, seeding, pesticide application and harvesting. In addition to machinery and labour costs, the tool also accounts for the costs of pesticide products based on the quantities applied and the unit price of each product.

Key technical inputs include machinery characteristics such as working width, operating speed, and energy consumption. These are combined with economic parameters like purchase price, service life, and maintenance and repair costs. The calculator covers more than 5,000 standardised field operations, each broken down into specific sub-tasks.

Labour costs for the machinery operator and variable costs such as fuel and lubricants are also incorporated. The tool first calculates machine costs on a per-hour basis, and then converts these into per-hectare costs using the estimated field capacity. A field efficiency factor is applied to account for typical time losses due to turning, waiting, and other interruptions.

The results are further refined based on field size, distance from the farm, and soil characteristics, all of which can significantly influence operational costs. A database containing pre-calculated records of different combinations of operations, machinery, and site-specific parameters enables the SUPPORT tool to generate cost estimates quickly and accurately.

The output includes clear, actionable economic indicators such as:

- Total cost per hectare
- Labor time per unit area
- A detailed breakdown of fixed and variable costs

These indicators help farm managers, consultants, and planners with decision-making, efficiency analysis, and budgeting.

Finally, the tool aggregates the costs of all operations across a field to produce economic metrics for the entire cropping strategy. A publicly accessible web service supports these calculations and is documented in detail at: <https://sf.julius-kuehn.de/wskosten/assets/swagger-dist/index.html>

3.5 Pesticide Load for Europe

The indicator presented here was developed for pesticide assessment at the European level. It aligns with the Danish Pesticide Load (PL-DK) and is referred to as the Pesticide Load Europe (PL-EU). The PL-EU, was developed and introduced as a new metric designed to assess the environmental and health impacts of pesticide used in EU Members States. It provides detailed methodologies for calculating the PL, incorporating factors related to human health, ecotoxicology, and environmental fate of pesticides. The PL is based on the inherent chemical properties of active ingredients as recorded in the Pesticide Properties Database (PPDB), and is therefore independent of the location where the active ingredient is applied. The PPDB is the most comprehensive database on pesticide properties and it is constantly updated. It has grown from 250 active ingredients in 2009 to 1,900 in 2025 (2,500 including metabolites and adjuvants) and spans over 320 properties.

3.5.1 Calculation of the PL-EU

The calculation of the PL-EU relies on a standardized and comprehensive database containing information on active ingredient properties and toxicity values. In this study, the Pesticide Properties Database (PPDB)²⁴ was used as the primary data source, ensuring consistency with the original PL methodology and enabling access to a wide range of parameters beyond ecotoxicological endpoints. The development of the PL-EU is also informed by ongoing collaboration and technical discussions with the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission and the German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt, UBA), both of which are actively working with the PPDB and contributing to pesticide risk assessment methodologies.

3.5.2. PL-EU on field or farm level

The proposed PL-EU is used to analyse different cropping strategies at field scale. When applied at the field or farm level, detailed field-specific data on pesticide use is necessary. The field- or farm-level application of the PL-EU is primarily suited for comparing different cropping strategies for a specific crop at field or farm level, rather than for assessing the overall pesticide-related risk at the member state level.

Applying the PL-EU indicator over successive years on the same field enables an assessment of the impact of entire crop rotations. To support this, field-specific pesticide application calendars are required in order to appropriately calculate the PL scores according to the applied doses of active ingredients.

At the field or farm level, the PL-EU is calculated by multiplying substance-specific risk indices with the corresponding application rates (AR_{Ai}). These values are then aggregated by summing all applications on the field over a single growing season or an entire crop rotation, using a weighted approach. This aggregation can be performed either separately for individual substance groups—such as herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, and other pesticides—or as a single overall value encompassing all groups.

$$PL-EU_{field} = \sum_{AI=}^{n AI} AR_{AI} * PL-EU_{AI}$$

Where:

$PL-EU_{field}$	Sum of risk indices weighted by application rates for all active substances applied on a specific field [load/ha]
AR_{AI}	Application rate of an active ingredient [kg/ha]
$PL-EU_{AI}$	Risk index of an active ingredient [load/kg]

3.5.3. Calculation of the PL-EU for active ingredients

To calculate the PL-EU, all active ingredients that were approved and sold in the EU since 2011 were included. In total, 504 active ingredients were listed, of which 467 could be linked to the Pesticide Properties Database (PPDB).

The basis for calculating potential risks is a comprehensive and complete database of active ingredient properties and toxicity values. For the calculation of the indicators presented here, the PPDB²⁴ was used as a standardized data source. An alternative data source for the information on active ingredients could be the EFSA OpenFoodTox²⁵ database.

The PL-EU of each metric for an individual active ingredient (PL_{AI}) is standardized, so the values will range between zero and one. A detailed description of the standardization of the indices is given in section 3.5.4.

The pesticide risk index ($PL-EU$) is divided into three sub-indicators: human health ($PL-EU_{Health}$), environmental behavior ($PL-EU_{EFate}$), and environmental ecotoxicity ($PL-EU_{ETox}$). These indicators are further broken down into sub-indicators based on specific active ingredient metric. A detailed description of the aggregation of the single AI indicator PL_{AI} is given in section 3.5.5.

3.5.3.1. Fate metrics

The fate metrics considered in the PL-EU are presented in Table 3. In addition to the original fate metrics of the PL-DK¹⁹, other metrics such as degradation in water ($DT50_{Water}$) was also be included to assess persistence. In the PL-DK, only soil degradation ($DT50_{soil}$) was used to describe persistence. In PL-EU, the average of these two metrics was employed as the load index for persistence. In the UK, work was also carried out to develop a UK pesticide load (PL-UK)²⁶, also based on the PL-DK like the PL-EU, and for the sake of comparison, the metrics included in the PL-UK are also shown in Tables 3-5.

Table 3: Fate metrics used to calculate PLfate

Metric	Description	Units	Max.	Min.	metric values available	coverage with values	PL-DK	PL-UK	PL-EU
Total number					467				
DT50soil	Persistence in soil is measured by DT ₅₀ , the time for a substance's concentration to decrease by 50%. Lab values are used for all AI	days	1587	0,001	314	67,2%	yes	yes	yes
DT50water	Persistence in water is measured by DT ₅₀ , the time for a substance's concentration to decrease by 50%.	days	1000	0,020	306	65,5%	no	no	yes
SCIGROW	The SciGrow evaluate the likelihood of groundwater contamination . It is a model used to estimate the potential of a substance to reach groundwater. It is based on physicochemical properties such as sorption (Koc) and degradation (DT ₅₀), along with standardized environmental scenarios. It evaluate the likelihood of groundwater contamination.	µg l ⁻¹	29,5549	0,000	287	61,5%	yes	no	yes
BCF	Bioaccumulation refers to a substance's tendency to concentrate within the tissues of organisms through chemical partitioning from water into an organic phase (e.g., fish tissue), measured in liters per kilogram (L/kg). When bioconcentration factor (BCF) data is unavailable, it is estimated using the log ₁₀ of the octanol-water partition coefficient (log Kow).	l kg ⁻¹	26858	0	327	70,0%	yes	yes	yes
KOC	Mobility is a substance's tendency to reach surface water, measured by the organic carbon sorption coefficient (Kfoc/Koc), with Kfoc preferred and Koc used if unavailable.	mL g ⁻¹	>100000	0,1	304	65,1%	yes	yes	Yes

3.5.3.2. Ecotoxicity metrics

The Table 4 presents an overview of the eco-toxicological metrics used for PL-EU which are used for calculation across 467 substances. It includes key information such as the range of metric values, data availability, and inclusion in previous studies^{19,26}.

Most aquatic toxicity metrics (e.g., LC₅₀ for fish, aquatic invertebrates, algae) have high data coverage (above 80%) and are included in both the PL-DK.¹⁹ and the PL-UK²⁶. Similarly, terrestrial toxicity metrics like LD₅₀ for birds, mammals, and bees also show high availability and inclusion.

Some metrics, such as those for sediment organisms, non-target plants, and certain beneficial insects (e.g., bumblebees, mason bees, ladybirds), have low data availability—often below 30%—and were not included in earlier frameworks. They were included in the PL-EU model.

Table 4: Ecotoxicity metrics used to calculate PL Ecotoxicity

Metric	Description	Units	Min.	Max.	metric values available	Perc. with values	PL-DK	PL-UK	PL-EU
Total number					467	100%			
LC50_FISH	Lethal concentration for 50% of fish population	mg l ⁻¹	0,000035	10000	421	90,1%	Yes	Yes	Yes
LC50_AQU_INVERT	Lethal concentration for 50% of aquatic invertebrates (water fleas, aquatic invertebrates).	mg l ⁻¹	0,000022	10000	423	90,6%	Yes	Yes	Yes
LC50_SEDIMENTORG.	Lethal concentration for 50% of sediment-dwelling organisms (benthic species).	mg l ⁻¹	0,000013	719	75	16,1%	No	No	Yes
LC50_ALGAE	Lethal concentration for 50% of algae population (toxicity to primary producers).	mg l ⁻¹	0,00004	3000	412	88,2%	Yes	Yes	Yes
EC50_LEMNA	Effective concentration for 50% of Lemna (duckweed) population (growth inhibition).	mg l ⁻¹	0,00011	301	258	55,2%	No	No	Yes
NOEC_FISCHE	No Observed Effect Concentration for fish	mg l ⁻¹	0,000004	10000	349	74,7%	Yes	Yes	Yes
NOEC_DAPHNIA	No Observed Effect Concentration for Daphnia	mg l ⁻¹	1,3E-06	420	340	72,8%	Yes	Yes	Yes
NOEC_SEDIMENTORG	No Observed Effect Concentration for sediment organisms.	mg l ⁻¹	0,000031	1000	175	37,5%	No	No	Yes
LC50_EARTHWORM	Lethal concentration for 50% of earthworm population	mg kg ⁻¹	0,855	6720	384	82,2%	Yes	Yes	Yes
NOEC_EARTHWORM	No Observed Effect Concentration for earthworms (chronic soil toxicity)	mg kg ⁻¹	0,0336	3550	281	60,2%	Yes	Yes	Yes
NOEC_OTHER_SOILORG	No Observed Effect Concentration for other soil organisms (e.g., collembolae)	mg kg ⁻¹	0,004	5000	169	36,2%	No	No	Yes
LD50_BIRDS	Lethal dose for 50% of bird population	mg kg ⁻¹	0,8	20000	404	86,5%	Yes	Yes	Yes
NOEL_BIRDS	Birds - Chronic 21d NOEL	(mg kg ⁻¹ bw d ⁻¹)	0,088	1440	219	46,9%	No	No	Yes
LD50_MAM_ORAL	Lethal dose for 50% of mammals via oral exposure.	mg kg ⁻¹	0,672	20000	433	92,7%	Yes	Yes	Yes
NOEL_MAM	Mammals - Chronic 21d NOEL	(mg kg ⁻¹ bw d ⁻¹)	0,3	4279	226	48,4%	No	No	Yes
LD50_BEE_CONT	Lethal dose for 50% of honeybees via contact exposure.	µg insect ⁻¹	0,001	1200	375	80,3%	Yes	Yes	Yes

Metric	Description	Units	Min.	Max.	metric values available	Perc. with values	PL-DK	PL-UK	PL-EU
LD50_BEE_ORA	Lethal dose for 50% of honeybees via oral exposure (e.g., ingestion of contaminated nectar).	µg insect ⁻¹	0,00184	2733	373	79,9%	No	No	Yes
LD50_BUMBLEBEE_CONT	Lethal dose for 50% of bumblebees via contact exposure.	µg insect ⁻¹	0,02	1161,6	68	14,6%	No	No	Yes
LD50_BUMBLEBEE_ORA	Lethal dose for 50% of bumblebees via oral exposure.	µg insect ⁻¹	0,005	1161,6	62	13,3%	No	No	Yes
LD50_MASONBEE_CONT	Lethal dose for 50% of mason bees via contact exposure.	µg insect ⁻¹	0,031	480	25	5,4%	No	No	Yes
LD50_MASONBEE_ORA	Lethal dose for 50% of mason bees via oral exposure.	µg insect ⁻¹	0,0003	125	10	2,1%	No	No	Yes
LR50_T_PYRI	Lethal rate for 50% of <i>Trichogramma pyralidae</i> (a parasitoid wasp species).	g/ha	0,0006	10000	306	65,5%	No	No	Yes
LR50_A_RHOPA	Lethal rate for 50% of <i>Aphidius rhopalosiphi</i> (a parasitoid wasp attacking aphids).	g/ha	0,01	10000	296	63,4%	No	No	Yes
LR50_P_CUPREUS	Lethal rate for 50% of <i>Poecilus cupreus</i> (a ground beetle species).	g/ha	2,45	10000	56	12,0%	No	No	Yes
LR50_C_CARNEA	Lethal rate for 50% of <i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> (green lacewing, beneficial predator).	g/ha	0,036	10000	94	20,1%	No	No	Yes
LR50_C_SEPTEMP	Lethal rate for 50% of <i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> (seven-spot ladybird, beneficial predator).	g/ha	0	7296	51	10,9%	No	No	Yes
ER50_NTP1	Effective concentration for 50% effect on non-target plants.	g/ha	0,054	10000	121	25,9%	No	No	Yes
ER50_NTP2	Effective concentration for 50% effect on non-target plants.	g/ha	0,00127	10000	96	20,6%	No	No	Yes

3.5.3.3. Human health metrics

The human health metrics, which can be used in PL-EU, are listed in Table 5. This table summarizes six key metrics related to human health toxicity and exposure for 467 substances. The most widely available metric is LD₅₀ for mammals via oral exposure, with 85% data coverage, followed closely by LD₅₀ via dermal exposure (84%). These values indicate the dose required to cause death in 50% of test mammals and are commonly used in human toxicological risk assessments.

Metrics related to occupational exposure focus on the risks faced by people applying or handling pesticides. The AOEL (Acceptable Operator Exposure Level), which indicates the maximum safe daily exposure over the long term, has data available for 79.6% of the active ingredients. MAC (Maximum Allowable Concentration), which defines the highest safe concentration in workplace air, has data for only 18,4% of substances—highlighting a significant gap in air exposure data. These metrics are crucial for evaluating the safety of pesticide use in professional settings.

Consumer safety is primarily assessed through ingestion-based metrics. The ADI (Acceptable Daily Intake), representing long-term exposure safety through diet, is available for 77.1% of substances. The ARfD (Acute Reference Dose), which assesses short-term or one-time dietary exposure, is available for 53.5% of substances. These metrics are essential for evaluating residues in food and ensuring consumer protection.

General mammalian toxicity is captured by LD₅₀ values, which measure the lethal dose required to kill 50% of test mammals. The oral LD₅₀ has the highest data availability at 92,7%, while the chronic NOEAL is nearly as complete with a data availability of 92,7%. These endpoints are widely used in toxicology to assess the baseline hazard of substances to mammals.

Table 5: Human health metrics used to calculate PL Human Health

Metric	Description	Units	Min.	Max.	metric values available	Perc. with values	PL-DK	PL-UK	PL-EU
Total number					467	100 %			
AOEL	Acceptable Operator Exposure Level: The maximum amount of a substance that a worker can be exposed to daily over a long period without harmful effects.	mg kg ⁻¹ bw d ⁻¹	1,2E-06	128	360	77,1%	no	no	yes
ARFD	Acceptable Operator Exposure Level: The estimated amount of a substance that can be ingested in a single day or meal without adverse health effects.	mg kg ⁻¹ bw d ⁻¹	0,0005	6,7	250	53,5%	no	no	yes
ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake: The estimated amount of a substance that can be ingested daily over a lifetime without significant health risk.	mg kg ⁻¹ bw d ⁻¹	0,00008	13,6	354	75,8%	no	no	yes
MAC	Maximum Allowable Concentration: This refers to the highest concentration of a substance allowed in workplace air that is considered safe for human exposure over a specific time period (usually an 8-hour workday).	mg kg ⁻¹ bw d ⁻¹	0,006	2000	86	18,4%	no	no	yes
LD50_MAM	Lethal dose for 50% of mammals via oral exposure.		0,672	20000	433	92,7%	no	no	yes
NOEAL_MAM	Mammals - Chronic 21d NOAEL	mg kg ⁻¹ bw d ⁻¹	0,3	4279	226	48,4%	no	no	yes

3.5.4. Calculation and standardisation of the pesticide loads

3.5.4.1. Fate metrics

The PL load scores for fate measures as persistence in soil ($DT50_{soil}$), bio concentration (BCF), Mobility (K_{oc}) and leachability to surface water (GUS) are derived using regulatory interpretation thresholds and reference substance values according to Rainford et al. (2022). In their analysis, the reference points were selected from known regulatory thresholds, marking transitions between low, intermediate, and high risk. Their placement on the 0 to 1 standardized scale ensures risk categories are evenly distributed. In this proposal, two additional metrics were included to describe the fate of active ingredients: degradation in water ($DT50_{water}$) and leachability to surface water (SciGrow).

Based on the thresholds, Rainford et al. (2022) generated standardization curves using linear interpolation between the reference values. In this approach, logarithmic or exponential fits to the reference values were used to convert the original metric values into load scores ranging from zero to one for each pesticide and fate metric.

3.5.4.2. Ecotoxicity and Human health metrics

For ecotoxicity and human health metrics, the pesticide property value of a given active ingredient is expressed relative to a reference substance as suggested in Kudsk et al. (2018). In this study, we suggest to use percentiles as reference values, which are based on all active ingredients considered in this study. These are based on data on pesticide sales reported to the Commission by Member States under Regulation (EC) No 1185/2009. In total, there were **504** AI from which **468** could be linked to the PPDB by the EU-code. For all active ingredient ecotoxicity metrics ($ETox_{AI}$) listed in Table 2, the reciprocal of both the parameter and the reference value is used, as a lower value indicates a higher risk.

$$PL-EU_{ToxMetric} = \frac{1}{\frac{Tox_{AI}}{Tox_{ref}}}$$

Where:

$PL-EU_{ToxMetric}$	Sub-indicator for one ecotoxicity metric
Tox_{AI}	ecotoxicity metric of an active ingredient parameter
Tox_{ref}	Reference value of the ecotoxicity metrics

The $PL-EU_{HH}$ is linked to the human health metrics listed in Table 5.

$$PL-EU_{HHmetric} = \frac{1}{\frac{HH_{AI}}{HH_{ref}}}$$

Where:

$PL-EU_{HHmetric}$	Sub-indicator for one human health metric
HH_{AI}	human health metric of an active ingredient
HH_{ref}	reference value of human health metrics

Following the discussion in our group, it was suggested that preserving the natural scaling of ecotoxicity and human health metrics was more important than the potential distortion caused by extreme reference substance values. As a result, regulatory thresholds have not been applied to ecotoxicity and human health load metrics.

3.5.5. Aggregation of the PL-EU

3.5.5.1. Aggregation of the fate load metrics

The PL_{Fate} score is calculated through a two-step aggregation process (Table 6). In the first step, the two metrics for persistence ($DT_{50\ soil}$ and $DT_{50\ water}$) are averaged. In the second step, the values for persistence, leachability, bio-concentration and mobility are combined using a simple average to determine the overall PL_{Fate} score.

Because the fate metrics differ significantly, and the first aggregation step involves combining inherently heterogeneous parameters (e.g., DT50_{soil} vs. DT50_{water}), no strong correlations among the components were observed. For this reason, averaging was chosen as the aggregation method.

Table 6: Aggregation of the Fate load metrics

PL Metrics for Fate	1st Aggregation		2nd Aggregation	
	Method	Group	Method	Group
DT50 _{soil}	as average → (2 metrics)	Persistence	as average → (4 metrics)	PL Fate
DT50 _{water}				
SCIGROW	no aggregation	Leachability		
BCF	no aggregation	Bio Concentration		
KOC	no aggregation	Mobility		

3.5.5.2. Aggregation of the ecotoxicity load metrics

The aggregation process is carried out in four distinct steps (Table 7). In the first step, we have chosen to select the minimum toxic value, or more specifically, the worst-case scenario, for a group of reference organisms that inhabit the same environmental compartment and constitute a homogeneous group. These reference organisms include aquatic plants, soil organisms, terrestrial plants, pollinators, mammals, and beneficial organisms.

By selecting the worst-case organism within a homogeneous group, we can reduce the occurrence of missing values in aggregated organism group data. For example, the two metrics for aquatic plants show data availability of 92% for algae and only 58% for *Lemna*. As a result, many active ingredients have values for algae but none for *Lemna*. This is expected, as *Lemna* tests are typically only conducted when algae toxicity is relatively high. By applying the worst-case toxicity approach - using the lowest value of the two metrics - we can still incorporate *Lemna* data, despite its lower availability. However, this also means we implicitly assume that the ranking of the *Lemna* toxicity data is not significantly different from that of the algae toxicity data. The strong correlation between the two metrics ($R^2 = 0.68$) for active ingredients where both values are available supports this assumption, indicating they generally reflect similar trends.

In the second aggregation step, these initial values are grouped further. Aquatic organisms are grouped into acute and chronic categories, based on four and three metrics respectively. Vertebrates are calculated as the average of two mammalian metrics, while pollinators, beneficial organisms and plants are maintained as separate groups.

In the second and third aggregation levels, we chose to aggregate using averages, as the groups involved are relatively heterogeneous. In these cases, we are grouping different organisms that inhabit distinct ecological compartments. By calculating the average, we ensure that an active ingredient with high toxicity for one metric and low toxicity for another will result in a lower PL-EU than an active ingredient that shows high toxicity across multiple metrics.

For example, if herbicide A is highly toxic to aquatic plants but shows low toxicity to the other three aquatic organisms, it should receive a lower PL-EU than a herbicide which, in addition to being highly

toxic to aquatic plants, also exhibits high toxicity toward one or more of the other aquatic organisms. Given the heterogeneity of the groups at aggregation levels 2, 3 and 4 we do not expect strong correlations between the metrics of each group. Using averaging as the aggregation method, rather than selecting the worst-case value, does not create an unfair advantage for an active ingredient with missing data.

In the third aggregation step, broader ecological categories are formed. Aquatic organisms are obtained by averaging the acute and chronic scores. Soil organisms are calculated by averaging three relevant organism groups. Terrestrial organisms are derived by averaging the scores for vertebrates, pollinators, beneficial organisms, and plants. Finally, in the fourth and last aggregation step, the overall PL Toxicity score is calculated by averaging the scores of the three main ecosystem-level groups: aquatic organisms, soil organisms, and terrestrial organisms. This method ensures a balanced and comprehensive representation of ecological toxicity across multiple environmental compartments.

Table 7: Aggregation of the Ecotoxicity load metrics

PL Metrics for Toxicity	1st Aggregation		2nd Aggregation		3rd Aggregation		4th Aggregation	
	Method	Group	Method	Group	Method	Group	Method	Group
LC50_FISH	no aggregation	Plants	as average → (4 metrics)	aquatic organisms acute	as average → (2 metrics)	aquatic organisms	as average → (3 metrics)	PL Toxicity
LC50_AQU_INVERTRATES								
LC50_SEDIMENT								
LC50_ALGAE	worst case as minimum → (2 metrics)							
ECS0_LEMNA								
NOEC_FISHE	no aggregation		as average → (3 metrics)	aquatic organisms chronic				
NOEC_AQU_INVERTRATES								
NOEC_SEDIMENT								
LC50_EARTHWORM	no aggregation				as average → (3 metrics)	soil organisms		
NOEC_EARTHWORM								
NOEC_OTHER_SOILORG								
LD50_Birds	worst case as minimum → (2 metrics)	Birds	as average → (2 metrics)	Vertebrates				
NOEL_BIRDS								
LD50_MAMALS_Oral	worst case as minimum → (2 metrics)	Mammals						
NOEAL_MAMALS								
LD50_BIENE_CONT	worst case as minimum → (6 metrics)	Pollinators	no aggregation	Pollinators	as average → (4 metrics)	terrestrial organisms		
LD50_BIENE_ORA								
LD50_BUMBLEBEE_CONT								
LD50_BUMBLEBEE_ORA								
LD50_MASONBEE_CONT								
LD50_MASONBEE_ORA								
LR50_T_PYRI	worst case as minimum → (5 metrics)	Beneficials	no aggregation	Beneficials				
LR50_A_RHOPA								
LR50_P_CUPREUS								
LR50_C_CARNEA								
LR50_C_SEPTEMP								
ER50_NTP1	worst case as minimum → (2 metrics)	Plants	no aggregation	Plants				
ER50_NTP2								

3.5.5.3 Aggregation of the human load metrics

The PL_{HH} score is calculated through a multi-step aggregation process (Table 8). First, the two metrics within each of the three groups, operators, consumers, and mammals, are aggregated using a worst-case (minimum) approach. The three aggregated values are then averaged to produce the PL_{HH} based on toxicity metrics.

Table 8: Aggregation of the Human Health load metrics

PL metrics for human health	1st Aggregation		2nd Aggregation	
	Method	Group	Method	Group
AOEL	worst case as minimum → (2 metrics)	Operators	as average → (3 metrics)	PL human health
MAC				
ADI	worst case as minimum → (2 metrics)	Consumers		
ARFD				
LD50_MAM_ORAL	worst case as minimum → (2 metrics)	Mammals		
NOEAL_MAMALS				

4. Discussion

During the development of SUPPORT IPM Monitoring Tool (SIM), it was decided not to calculate an aggregated risk indicator (PL_{Total}). This decision was driven primarily by significant methodological uncertainties associated with combining highly heterogeneous sub-indicators (environmental fate, ecotoxicity, and human health metrics). Aggregating diverse indicators could potentially lead to misleading conclusions and compromise the transparency of individual risk components. Consequently, emphasis was placed on presenting distinct sub-indicators separately to ensure clarity and provide a detailed understanding of specific risk dimensions.

Furthermore, SIM-Tool is primarily suited for comparisons at the field or farm level. The SIM-Tool was designed specifically to serve as a decision support mechanism, enabling stakeholders—particularly farmers—to evaluate different agricultural strategies, especially regarding the implementation of IPM measures. By clearly visualizing the ecological, economic, and health impacts of adopting IPM strategies, this approach aims to motivate farmers toward more sustainable agricultural practices.

It is important to note that comparisons across different countries have limited relevance. National differences in pesticide authorization and availability and cropping conditions can significantly influence the calculated risk values, leading to potential misinterpretations. Meaningful international comparisons would require harmonized regulatory frameworks and agricultural conditions, which currently are not uniformly established across countries.

Overall, the developed methodology provides potential to facilitate dialogue among science, policy, and practice, promoting evidence-based decisions and ultimately supporting the transition toward more sustainable pest management systems.

5. Outlook and Further Development

The first validation round took place in April 2025, during which scenario comparison outputs were generated for each NCC based on the data provided. These results were shared with the respective NCC partners and discussed in detail, offering valuable feedback on the tool's performance, indicator outputs, and overall usability.

The next phase in the development of the SIM Tool focuses on stakeholder validation and iterative refinement based on user feedback. A second validation round will be conducted during July and August 2025. During this period, NCC partners will be invited to explore the tool independently, gaining familiarity with its functions and practicing data input and result generation. This phase aims to ensure that users are well-prepared to apply the tool effectively and identify any usability issues or points of confusion.

This validation period will feed directly into the third Focus Group meeting scheduled for September 4th, 2025, as part of the internal WP4 meeting. NCC partners will have the opportunity to present their experiences with the tool and provide feedback on both content and functionality. Based on this exchange, minor adjustments to the user interface and tool documentation will be made, ensuring smooth preparation for the third and final round of national focus groups. These focus groups, which will take place between October and December 2025, will involve stakeholders using the SIM Tool to co-develop novel IPM strategies adopting future IPM tools that currently are in their initial phases in terms of development and/or implementation. The reporting on these activities will be completed by February 2026, allowing JKI to conduct a comprehensive analysis of proposed strategies using the tool.

An updated version of the SIM Tool, reflecting all stakeholder input and technical refinements, is scheduled for release in October 2026 (Month 46). This version will serve as a consolidated outcome of the SUPPORT project's collaborative development process.

Looking further ahead, efforts are underway to explore the incorporation of site-specific pesticide risk assessment, based on the SYNOPSIS¹⁸ approach. The SYNOPSIS model enables realistic risk assessments of pesticide applications under local conditions by incorporating detailed data on soil type, crop type, weather data, surface water proximity, and pesticide properties. Integrating this functionality into the SIM Tool would enable a more precise evaluation of aquatic exposure risk at the field level, thus improving the spatial resolution and relevance of the environmental risk indicators.

6. SIM Tool User Guide

1. Go to the following link: <http://synops.julius-kuehn.de/support>
Create a new account by signing up.

2. Select your agricultural field area in the “Agricultural Fields” section (red box in figure).

2.1 Click **“Layers”** and then **“Map Type”** to switch to OpenStreetMap, if desired. Please note that the remaining layers are only available in Germany.

2.2 Zoom to your region and click **“New”** to create a new entry.

Choose option “Select new site from geometry”

Zoom in to the desired area and click to define the field boundaries. The area in hectares will be calculated automatically.

Tip: The background maps are provided via Google Maps and OpenStreetMap, ensuring global coverage and regular updates.

Name the field and save it. It will be stored under “Agricultural Fields”.

All created field areas will appear under **“Agricultural Fields”**. By clicking on the right symbol , you can link it directly to an application scenario (see Section 3), or choose to edit or delete it.

3. Create an “Application Scenario” for each crop

3.1 Click on **“Application Scenarios”**, then select **“New”**.

Tip: To compare different scenarios for the same crop and crop cycle, you need to create a separate application pattern for each scenario. For example, to compare a conventional wheat scenario with an IPM scenario, create two distinct application scenarios.

Create a link to a field you defined in Step 2.

3.2 Complete the required fields, then click **“Save”**. When entering the crop in the **“Search Crop”** field, a drop-down list will appear as soon as you start typing. Simply begin typing the crop name, and the tool will suggest matching entries for you to select from.

3.3 Begin entering all field operations along with the corresponding machinery.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

New application

1 New application

2 Resources on ...

Sowing

PPP

Non-chemical control measures

TILLAGE

HARVEST

Catch/Cover crops

Procedure / Measure

Technique

Date * 2020

Notes

Notes

Details

Working width [m]

Diesel price [€/l] 1.2

Hourly wage [€/h] 12

User name Name

(*) Required

Mitigation measures

Tillage No mulch

Contour farming

Coarse seedbed preparation

Covercrop

(*) Required

NEXT

Tip: The diesel price (€/l) and hourly wage (€/h) are pre-filled with default values but can be customized. These figures are used to calculate the final cost estimate. The working width (m) is automatically retrieved based on the selected machine type under “Technique”. You may also add mitigation measures for additional context—this step is optional.

3.4 Sowing

3.4.1. Select a procedure from the list:

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

New application

1 New application

2 Resources on ...

Sowing

PPP

Non-chemical control measures

TILLAGE

HARVEST

Catch/Cover crops

Procedure / Measure

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with direct seed drill

Technique

Mulch sowing of wheat, field beans, peas

Date *

Notes

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with direct seed drill

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with tiller and seeder

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with cultivator, rotary harrow and seed drill

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with rotary harrow and seed drill

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with seedbed combination and seeder

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with a seed drill

Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with tine rotor and seeder

Sowing of winter wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans as ridge crop

3.4.2 Select a technique (machine details), choose a date and click “Next”. Each technique includes key machine specifications such as working width (in meters) and engine power (in kilowatts, kW).

Technique

3 m; 67 kW

Date *

Notes

3 m; 102 kW

3 m; 120 kW

3 m; 54 kW

3 m; 67 kW

3 m; 83 kW

4 m; 102 kW

4 m; 120 kW

4 m; 138 kW

4 m; 54 kW

3.4.3 Enter the required fields: Seed density (seeds/m²) and Thousand Seed Weight. A default value is provided for each crop for both fields. It is also possible to input the seed density in kg/ha.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

- 1 New application
- 2 Resources on 3.4.

Resources on 3.4.

Variety

Seed/planting density in kg/ha

Seed density [Seeds/m²]*

Thousand Seed Weight (45-55)*

PPP Price [€/kg]

coating

(*) Required

3.5. Pesticide Applications (Plant Protection Products - PPP)

3.5.1 Complete the required fields: Date, Area (%), and Drift Reduction (%). Please enter this information separately for each PPP application.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

- 1 New application
- 2 Resources on ..

New application

Sowing

PPP

Non-chemical control measures

TILLAGE

HARVEST

Catch/Cover crops

Procedure / Measure

Technique

Date*

Area [%](from 9.0533 ha)*

Area in [ha]

Drift reduction*

Distance to water body [m]

Amount of water [l/ha]

Notes

NEXT

Tip: The Area (%) indicates the proportion of the field treated with the pesticide. Additional optional inputs include the distance to the water body (m) and the amount of water applied (l/ha).

3.5.2. Select one Technique from the list.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

New application

1 New application

2 Resources on ..

Sowing

PPP

Non-chemical control measures

TILLAGE

HARVEST

Catch/Cover crops

Procedure / Measure Plant protection

Technique

Date *

Area [%](von 9.0533 ha) *

Area in [ha]

Drift reduction *

Distance to water body [m]

Amount of water [l/ha]

- Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 12 m, 600 l; 37 kW
- Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 12 m, 600 l; 45 kW
- Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 15 m, 1.000 l; 45 kW
- Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 15 m, 1.000 l; 54 kW
- Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 15 m, 1.000 l; 67 kW
- Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 18 m, 1.500 l; 67 kW
- Tractor-mounted plant protection sprayer, 21 m, 3.000 l; 54 kW
- Tractor-mounted plant protection sprayer, 21 m, 3.000 l; 67 kW
- Tractor-mounted plant protection sprayer, 21 m, 3.000 l; 83 kW

Tip: Each Technique includes the machine type, working width (meters), tank capacity (litres) and engine power (kW)

3.5.3. Add Resources

Option A: Search for the commercial pesticide product name.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

Resources on 5.7.

+ ← Please add Resources

↓

Search for product

Search Commercial Product
 Search Active Ingredient (AI)

PPP/AI

Appl. rate [g/ha]/[ml/ha] 0

PPP Price [€/kg] 0

Notes

CANCEL ADD RESOURCES

Tip: If the product is in the German database, it will be suggested automatically.

Then, enter the application rate and pesticide price per kg or L and finally click **“Add Resources”**.

The screenshot shows a search interface with the following elements:

- Search for product:** A text input field containing "roundup".
- Search Options:** Two radio buttons: "Search Commercial Product" (selected) and "Search Active Ingredient (AI)".
- Search Results:** A list of products with their names and codes:
 - Roundup 60 (007702-60)
 - Roundup AC (024345-72) - highlighted
 - Roundup AC Konzentrat (008529-62)
 - Roundup Alphée (043959-00)
 - Roundup Easy (034883-00)
 - Roundup Express (006921-60)
 - Roundup Future (00A042-00)
 - Roundup PowerFlex (006149-00)
 - Roundup REKORD (007525-60)
 - Roundup Speed (005316-00)
- Form Fields:** Input fields for "PPP/AI", "Appl. rate [g/ha]/[ml/ha]", and "PPP Price [€/kg]".
- Notes:** A text area for additional information.
- Buttons:** "CANCEL" and "ADD RESOURCES".

Option B: If the commercial pesticide product is unavailable in the German database, add the name of the active ingredient (AI) instead.

Click on **“Search Active Ingredient (AI)”**, enter the active ingredient, and choose it from the list.

The screenshot shows a search interface with the following elements:

- Search for product:** A text input field containing "glypho".
- Search Options:** Two radio buttons: "Search Commercial Product" and "Search Active Ingredient (AI)" (selected).
- Search Results:** A list of active ingredients:
 - glyphosate (1071-83-6)
 - glyphosate-trimesium (81591-81-3)
- Form Fields:** The "PPP/AI" field is populated with "glyphosate".

Tip: The tool includes all active ingredients from the Pesticide Properties Database (PPDB). If you want to add a biostimulant, simply type “biostimulant.” If the active ingredient is not listed and it’s a no-risk biopesticide, you can enter “no risk dummy.” This allows it to be accounted for without increasing pesticide risk.

To calculate the applied amount of active ingredient (AI), click on **“Calculate application rate from PPP”**

- ✓ Enter the application rate of the product (e.g., 1000).
- ✓ Enter the percentage of active ingredient in the product (e.g., 30%).

The dose of the active ingredient will be calculated automatically.

Finally, enter the pesticide price and click **“Add Resources”**.

Search for product

Search Commercial Product
 Search Active Ingredient (AI)

PPP/AI

Calculate application rate from PPP

Appl. rate [g/ha]/[ml/ha]

% of active ingredient in pesticide

Amount of AI [g/ha]/[ml/ha]

PPP Price [€/kg]

If you apply more than one product or active ingredient at the same time, click **“Add Application”** and enter the details as before. When finished, click **“Finish”**.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario Resources on 5.7. ×

1 New application
2 Resources on 5.7.

← Please add Resources

Name	Appl. rate	Indication	Link to BVL-database
glyphosate	300		1071-83-6 <input type="button" value="edit"/> <input type="button" value="X"/>

3.6 Overview of application scenarios

All field operations will appear in chronological order. If the same PPP applications are repeated on different dates (for example, the same fungicide applied four times during a crop cycle), you can use the “Copy/Paste” function for each entry. When applications are identical (same pesticide and amount), only the date needs to be changed. This speeds up the process of adding multiple PPP applications.

To add more field operations, please click on the button in the upper left corner.

Copy	Date	Procedure / Measure	Technique	Area	Drift reduction	Distance surface water	Filter strip	Buffer zone	Application map
	October 1 2020	Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with direct seed drill	3 m; 54 kW						
	November 3 2020	Plant protection	Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 15 m, 1.000 l; 67 kW	100 [%]	75 [%]	5 [m]	0[m]	5 [m]	
	April 6 2021	Mulching	2 m; 54 kW	100					

3.8 Add Non-chemical control measures

Choose a procedure and a technique from the lists, select the date, and click “**Finish**”.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

1 New application

New application

Sowing PPP Non-chemical control measures TILLAGE HARVEST Catch/Cover crops

Procedure / Measure

Technique

Date (*)Required

Flaming
Hoeing with a star hoe
Mulching
Harrowing
Harrowing with a bed harrow
Harrowing with a rolling harrow
Rolling, grassland

Details

ADD APPLICATION FINISH

3.9 Add Tillage

Choose a procedure and a technique from the lists, select the date, and click **“Finish”**.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

1 New application

Sowing PPP Non-chemical control measures **TILLAGE** HARVEST Catch/Cover crops

Procedure / Measure

Technique

Date (*)Required

Details

Harrows with spring tine harrow (mounted)

Harrowing with chain disc harrow

Harrowing with a rotary harrow

Harrowing with short disc harrow

Harrows with ring edge, inclined (30°)

Harrows with seedbed combination, mounted

Harrows with seedbed combination, mounted

Harrows with disc harrow, shallow

Harrowing with disc harrow, deep

Harrowing with spade roller harrow

ADD APPLICATION FINISH

3.10 Add Harvest

Choose a procedure and a technique from the lists, select the date, add yield and click **“Finish”**.

Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario

1 New application

Sowing PPP Non-chemical control measures TILLAGE **HARVEST** Catch/Cover crops

Procedure / Measure CCM harvest with transfer wagon; straw chopped

Technique

Date 2021

Yield [t/ha] 0

Notes

ADD APPLICATION FINISH

3.11 Add Cover crops

Please add a catch crop if you plant a fast-growing crop between main crops to protect the soil or improve fertility.

Choose a procedure and a technique from the lists, select the date and click **“Next”**.

The screenshot shows the 'New application' form. On the left, a sidebar lists '1 New application' and '2 Resources on 3.5.'. The main form area has a title 'New application' and a close button. Below the title are six icons representing different agricultural practices: Sowing, PPP, Non-chemical control measures, TILLAGE, HARVEST, and Catch/Cover crops. The 'Catch/Cover crops' icon is highlighted with a blue dashed border. Below the icons, there are dropdown menus for 'Procedure / Measure' (selected: 'Mulch sowing of wheat, field beans, peas'), 'Technique' (selected: '3 m; 138 kW'), and 'Date' (selected: '3', 'MAI', '2021'). There is a 'Notes' text area and a red asterisk indicating a required field. At the bottom right, there is a blue 'NEXT' button.

Select the cover crop using the **“Search for crop”** field, then enter the appropriate seeding rate. Once completed, click on **“Add resources”** to include the crop in your plan.

The screenshot shows the 'Resources on 3.5.' form. On the left, the sidebar lists '1 New application' and '2 Resources on 3.5.'. The main form area has a title 'Resources on 3.5.' and a blue plus icon with a left arrow and the text 'Please add Resources'. A large red arrow points down to the 'Search for crop' field. Below it is the 'Seeding rate (kg/ha)' field with a value of '0' and a dropdown arrow. At the bottom, there are two buttons: 'CANCEL' and 'ADD RESOURCES'.

3.12 Finalizing all application measures for one scenario

After adding all field operations, the overview will look like this (simplified example):

The screenshot shows the 'Applications Test_Wheat_IPM_scenario [winter soft wheat]' interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with a search bar and a '+ New' button. The main area displays a table of field operations with the following data:

	Date	Procedure / Measure	Technique	Area	Drift reduction	Distance surface water	Filter strip	Buffer zone	Application map
<input type="checkbox"/>	October 1 2020	Sowing wheat, field beans, peas; soybeans with direct seed drill	3 m; 54 kW						
<input type="checkbox"/>	November 3 2020	Plant protection	Cultivation plant protection sprayer, 15 m, 1.000 l; 67 kW	100 [%]	75 [%]	5 [m]	0[m]	5 [m]	
<input type="checkbox"/>	April 6 2021	Mulching	2 m; 54 kW	100					
<input type="checkbox"/>	July 1 2021	CCM harvest with takeover and transport to the farm; straw chopped	Double trailer each 18 t, three-way tipping trailer; 120 kW						

Since the main purpose of the tool is to compare two or more scenarios for the same crop, you will need to add one or more additional application scenarios. You can do this by starting a new scenario using **“New”** (see above) or by duplicating the current scenario and modifying the copy. Each application scenario can be edited or deleted as needed.

Tip: If the scenarios you’re comparing are similar, it’s recommended to duplicate an existing application scenario and modify the copy to save time on data entry.

4. Analysis

Once you have two or more scenarios for the same crop in “**Application Scenarios**”, you can start analysing the results. Click on the “**Analysis**” section. All application scenarios will appear on the left, listed under each agricultural field area.

The analysis includes four sections for each scenario: Risk, PL-EU, Costs, and GHG; plus one section for comparing selected scenarios called “**Compare**”.

You can always link an application scenario to an agricultural area by clicking here:

4.1 Risk Overview

The Risk tab includes the following information for each scenario:

- Number of PPP: Total number of pesticide products and active ingredients applied
- Quantity applied: Total amount of all pesticide products and active ingredients (kg/ha).
- Expected yield (t/ha)
- Frequency of pesticide applications: Number of times spraying operations were conducted, meaning how many times the machinery passed over the field applying pesticide products. Note that multiple products can be applied during a single pass, but this count only includes instances when spraying equipment was actively used.
- Overview of the selected field area
- Empty boxes: these sections are still under development and should be left blank for now
- PL-EU: Pesticide Load (see section 3.5 of the main document for calculation details)

- Total Costs (€/ha): See section 3.4 of the main document for calculation details
- Total GHG emissions (kg/ha): See section 3.3 of the main document for calculation details

4.2 Pesticide Load (PL-EU)

For each scenario, the Pesticide Load (PL) is calculated based on three main subcomponents: PL Human Health, PL Fate, and PL Ecotoxicology. PL Ecotoxicology is further divided into PL Aquatic, PL Soil, and PL Terrestrial organisms.

All pesticide products used and their corresponding active ingredients will appear in this section.

For details on the PL calculation, please refer to the section 3.5 of the main document.

Risk	Risk per AI	PL-EU	Costs	GHG	Compare			
Product	Active Ingredient	PL-EU _{HumanTotal}	PL-EU _{FateTotal}	PL-EU _{EcotoxTotal}	PL-EU _{AquaticTotal}	PL-EU _{SoilTotal}	PL-EU _{TerrestrialTotal}	
Bandur	Aclonifen	559.42	882.32	227.65	113.94	109.38	459.62	
Quickdown	Pyraflufen	0.16	2.21	0.76	2.07	0.11	0.09	
Sencor Liquid	Metribuzin	132.29	279.21	21.93	14.82	14.96	36.02	
Infinito	Propamocarb	37.42	366.93	6.50	0.04	14.28	5.18	
Infinito	Fluopicolide	18.72	74.89	1.24	2.18	1.10	0.46	
Sum		839.9148	1605.5712	748.0059	133.05072	139.81992	501.358	

4.3 Costs

For each scenario, all field operations are listed as shown below (extract). Each measure includes a cost calculation per hectare, considering machine costs, input costs, and labor costs for the procedure (both per hectare and total for the field area).

For more details on cost calculations, please refer to the section 3.4 of the main document.

Risk	PLI-EU	Costs	GHG	Compare					
	Date	Machine costs for the procedure per hectare	Machine costs for the procedure	Costs of inputs for the procedure per hectare	Costs of inputs for the procedure	Working hours for the procedure per hectare	Working hours for the procedure per hectare	Total costs for the procedure	
	15.9.	69.28 €/ha	627.21 €	0.00 €/ha	0.00 €	0.73 €/ha	79.31 €	706.51 €	
	1.10.	19.55 €/ha	177.03 €	20.00 €/ha	181.07 €	0.52 €/ha	56.49 €	414.58 €	
	5.10.	6.92 €/ha	62.68 €	30.75 €/ha	278.39 €	0.13 €/ha	14.12 €	355.19 €	

4.4 Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions

For each scenario, all field operations are listed as shown below (extract). Each measure includes a calculation of cumulative energy use and GHG emissions per hectare, considering machinery, diesel consumption, and input materials.

For more details on GHG emission calculations, please refer to the section 3.3 of the main document.

Risk	PLI-EU	Costs		GHG	Compare							
		Date	Cumulative energy use (MJ/ha)			GHG Emissions (kg/ha)						
			Machine	Diesel	Material	Input materials		Machine	Diesel	Material	Input materials	
					PPP/Fertilization/Sowing	total				PPP/Fertilization/Sowing	Area emissions	total
	15.9.	167.73	877.00	0.00	-	1,044.73	11.82	53.69	0.00	-	0.00	65.52
	1.10.	42.48	208.00	0.00	469.20	719.68	2.99	12.75	0.00	15.85	0.00	31.59
	5.10.	18.56	40.00	0.00	125.71	184.27	1.31	2.44	0.00	5.51	0.00	9.26

4.5 Comparing scenario outputs

Clicking on **“Compare”** and then **“Table”** displays a comparison table. This table includes all selected scenarios and all indicators from section 4.1.

Click **“Export”** to download the table as a CSV file.

Scenario	N° Pesticide products	N° Active ingredients	Frequency of pesticide applications	Expected yield (t/ha)	Total costs (€/ha)	Total GHG emissions (kg/ha)	PL Human	PL Fate	PL Ecotoxicology	PL Aquatic	PL Soil	PL Terrestrial
Potato_GER_S1_IPM	4	5	4	15	91.15	683.13	748.01	1,605.57	258.08	133.05	139.82	501.36
Potato_GER_S1_Stateofart	7	10	7	15	334.98	683.11	805.62	1,804.42	284.34	138.40	168.05	546.58
Potato_GER_S2_IPM	11	13	11	40	374.25	698.27	1,156.05	3,348.55	308.27	142.67	231.06	551.08
Potato_GER_S2_Stateofart	11	13	11	40	366.29	694.31	1,156.05	3,348.55	308.27	142.67	231.06	551.08

Tip: You can choose which scenarios to compare by toggling the selection

The same results can be visualized by clicking on **“Plots”**, where each bar color corresponds to a different scenario.

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